

Template Change Request - Complete

Request ID:	
Change Requester:	Name of the person or team requesting the change
Approval Responsible:	Name of the PO, PM, or responsible stakeholder
Request Date:	Date the request was submitted
Affected System Version:	e.g., v1.2.0
Type of Change:	Bug fix, improvement, new feature, customization, other
Change Category:	FR (Functional Requirement), NFR (Non-Functional Requirement), interface, process, documentation, other
Detailed Description:	Explanation of the need and context
Change Impact	
Does it impact existing requirements?	Yes/No
Impacted or related requirements:	Indicate related FRs or NFRs
Does it impact the project scope?	Yes/No
Schedule Impact:	Describe estimated impact on timeline
Cost Impact:	Indicate if additional budget or funding is required
Team Effort Impact:	Estimated hours or additional resources needed
Technically Feasible?	Yes/No
Feasibility and Impact Analysis Notes:	Risks, dependencies, limitations, or alternative solutions evaluated
Acceptance Criteria:	How will we know the change has been implemented correctly?
Priority:	High/Medium/Low
Registered in the backlog:	Yes/No
Change Request Status:	Not started ▾